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The Effect of Loan Policies and Recovery Expenditures on the Sustainability of Microfinance Institutions in the Ndian and Meme Divisions of the South West Region in Cameroon

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Abstract

Many see microfinance institutions as an answer to low income earners, a means to promote economic development, employment and growth as these institutions help support small businesses through microcredit. This study looked at the effect of loan policies on the sustainability of microfinance institutions in Ndian and Meme Divisions of the South West. Microcredit deals with the provision of loan facilities to the low income earners. Adopted the lending and performance theories of modern portfolio theory, and credit risk theory the study formulated a relationship between Loan delinquency as a measure of sustainability and the loan policies in place. A COBAC regulation was measured using a scale of 14 prudential norms. Technique of analysis was panel data where the fixed and random effects were estimated on a sample of 22 micro finance institutions for six years (2015-2020). The nature of the data in the study was primary data collected using questionnaires. The targeted population of the study was category one and two microfinance institutions in Ndian and Meme Division. The result of the study revealed that loan delinquency has significant impact on sustainability of microfinance institutions. The study went further to conclude that when there is high loan delinquency in a microfinance institution, the sustainability of the institutions staggers and when loan delinquency reduces the microfinance becomes more sustainable. The study recommended that microfinance institutions portfolios management strategies should focus more on the internal causes of delinquency which they have more control over and seek practical and achievable solutions to redress delinquency problems. It was also imperative for regulatory authorities to devise strategies to strengthen microfinance institutions financial position as well as ensuring enabling environment that will enhance the achievement of microfinance social objectives.

Key words: Loan Policies, Microfinance Institutions, Ndian and Meme

1. Introduction

The notion of microfinance has its roots from the 19th century when the theorist Lysander Spooner wrote over on the merits from small credits to entrepreneurs and farmers as a means of alleviating poverty. The concept gained great impact with the Marshall plan after the Second World War. Pioneers of this concept in the 1970s include Grameen Bank of Bangladesh, Mohammad Yunus (receiver of the Nobel Prize, 2006), Akhtar Hammeed

Khan, Shorebank in Chicago, Friedrich Wilhelm Raiffeise's village bank movement in Germany, Caisse Populaire Movement by Alphone and Dorimene Desjardins in Quebec. In February 1997, the first Microcredit Summit was launched by RESULTS Educational Fund (REF) which was a one year campaign to access 100 million poor homes of the world especially the women of such homes with microfinance facilities by the end of 2005.

Many see microfinance as an answer to low income earners, a means to promote economic development, employment and growth as these institutions help support small businesses through microcredit. The survival of these institutions is therefore very vital for economic growth and poverty alleviation.

In Cameroon, the history of microfinance dates back to more than one century in its traditional form popularly known as "Njangi or Tontine". The introduction of "modern" microfinance in Cameroon started in 1963 by a Catholic Priest Father Alfred Jansen, in Njinikom in the North-West Region of Cameroon (Creusot, 2006). This idea of Credit Unionism spread all over the North-West and South-West regions of Cameroon and by 1968, 34 credit unions that were already in existence joined together to form the Cameroon Cooperative Credit Union League (CamCCUL) Limited. CamCCUL is therefore the umbrella organization of cooperative credit unions and the largest microfinance institutions in Cameroon and the "Communauté Économique des États de l'Afrique Centrale" (CEMAC) sub-region (www.camccul.org).

Today it is a highly utilized means of financial assistance and survival for most low income earners especially in least developed nations where the economy does not permit citizen the luxury of commercial banking institutions. Petty traders, house wives and even students can save, borrow and even transfer funds at affordable interest rates through such microfinance institutions.

In Cameroon, Micro Financial Institutions (MFIs) dominate the financial sector and news of MFIs closure or having liquidity problems make prominent headlines in most newspapers and television channels. Institutions that were created under the premise of poverty alleviation are becoming tools to get the poor trapped in poverty. Microfinance has been exploited and will continue to be exploited by major stakeholders in the microfinance value chain who preach the same doctrine- that of poverty alleviation. While applause should be granted to institutions like the Community Bank Network (MC²), the Credit Union Network of CAMCCUL and the "Crédit Communautaire D'Afrique" (CCA), news of the creation of new microfinance institution and closure of existing microfinance institutions are very common. As a result, most citizens view microfinance institutions as chameleon institutions while others have been fast to classify microfinance institutions as 'sunrise and sunset' institutions which means, they go operational at sunrise and at sunset they do not exist. This alone has weakened customers' faith and confidence in these institutions although microfinance institutions remain the main source of financial services for the large group of the country's population (Fotabong, 2016). However, of late, there have been complains by the microfinance institutions regarding high rate of delinquency by their clients; which

presupposes that most microfinance institutions achieving the internationally accepted standard portfolio at risk of 3%, which is a cause for concern because of its consequences on businesses, individuals, and the economy of Cameroon at large.

The study therefore seeks to examine the effect of loan policies and recovery expenditures on the sustainability of microfinance institutions in Ndian and Meme Divisions of the South West Region in Cameroon. The study also investigates how regulations and expenses on loans recovered impact the sustainability of these microfinance institutions.

2. Literature Review

Two major concepts were used in this study are the Concept of Loan Delinquency and the Concept of Sustainability of Microfinance Institutions. The conceptual framework below acts as a road map and direction of research undertaking, it also guides the researcher towards his objectives (Magher, 2017).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Author 2021

The above diagram of conceptual framework shows how the variables are related. The Status of loans (delay payment of loans), expenses on loans recovered and the role on regulation are independent variables that will impact loan delinquency.

The theories mobilized for this study include the modern portfolio theory, liquidity theory of credit, credit risk theory, tax theory of credit and credit default theory.

Literature on delay payment of loans

Theodosios A. (2020) in Greece carried out a survey “on incorporating sustainability considerations into lending decisions and the management of bad loans” and a mixed methods approach of online questionnaires and semi-structured interview was utilized to link and investigate managerial perspectives of sustainability risk management and their impact on bad loans. The result of this survey indicates that every type of financial intermediary represented by their managers, coming from all levels of the organizational hierarchy, acknowledges the importance of sustainability-oriented private lending.

The executives' responses revealed that sustainability risk management indeed exist, but it has yet to penetrate core processes. It does provide strong motives over new management techniques and contributes to higher level of materiality of financial intermediaries' core operations.

Paul H. (2016) in Scotland found that late payment has wide range of consequences for companies, including deferring investments and innovation plans, being unable to access finance and discouraging trading internationally, all of which act as a drag on economic and productivity growth. Research offers insights into how companies can mitigate the effects and reduce the extent to which it is common practice, both those experiencing late payment and those adopting late payment practices.

From the above, one could see clearly that late payment of loans actually increases loan delinquency and increase cost of operations in microfinance institutions.

In terms of changing the behavior of those employing late payment practices, this paper has highlighted there is no simple fix as it appears to be driven as much by conventional norms and business culture than a deliberate power play.

The responses of governments in UK and across Europe fall short of compliance, and focus on education and encouragement. There is some emerging evidence that education and encouragement is making a difference, but perhaps not at the speed desired.

Ruth E. et al. (2019) in Cameroon conducted a study on Microfinance survival: 'the impact of credit management on the sustainability of microfinance institution in Cameroon'.

In this survey data was collected using questionnaires, direct observation and secondary data. Data analysis is descriptive. Results show that there were a good number of lapses like: high provision, poor recovery procedure, credit officers without an educational background in the field, manual execution of some loans, slow credit management processes, bad faith of customers and poor follow up of loans given out.

From the above internal factors, it indicates that due to loan delinquency, high provision has to be created and high provisioning increases cost as the income statement and the balance sheet are both affected. Since recovery of delinquent loans is not properly done the chances of loans becoming delinquent increases because of poor recovery procedures. Of course, credit officers without educational background will definitely not be able to properly analyse borrowers' capacity to repay loans before granting hence increasing loan delinquency of microfinance institutions. This will impact the sustainability of these microfinance institutions.

According to Gideon A. (2018) in Ghana in which descriptive research was the appropriate research design to use, purposive sampling was used for the selection of the managers (respondents) of the various microfinance institutions.

The research found that several institutions struggle with high default rates and also charged high interest rates. Bank of Ghana which is the Central Bank of the country has set rules and guidelines which regulate the establishment and the management of the microfinance institutions. Bank of Ghana has increased the minimum capital requirements (start-up capital) of these microfinance institutions which has a negative

influence on their sustainability. The introduction of financial technology in Ghana's financial sector has an influence on the sustainability of microfinance institutions. Financial technology such as mobile money has a positive influence on microfinance institutions in Ghana since these institutions have taken advantage of this technology to increase their profit margin.

Literature on expenses on loans recovered

Zahid et al. (2014) in Bangladesh carried out study on cost structure and financial sustainability of microfinance institutions. The methodology used management accounting ideas and frameworks, principally contingency theory to identify components of microfinance institutions cost structure, this study measures operational self-sufficiency as the result of administrative costs, financial costs, interest rate spread and size complexity. The results suggest that there are two key factors that are significantly related to microfinance institutions sustainability. Interest rate spread and general administrative costs. It was concluded that microfinance institutions that have lower administrative cost and a large interest rate spread are more likely to achieve sustainability prior to the introduction of the interest gap.

Beatrice N. (2012) in Kenya conducted a survey on factors affecting loan delinquency in microfinance institutions, a survey research design was used and a census of 49 microfinance institutions was taken. The data was collected through a self-developed structured questionnaire and administered to microfinance loan officers for response. Multiple regression analysis was used to establish relationship between loan delinquency and microfinance institution, self-help groups and external factors in microfinance institutions in Kenya.

The estimated regression coefficients and t-values were interpreted. The study found evidence that there exist a positive significant ($\beta = 9.937$, t-value = 5.016) relationship between loan delinquency and microfinance institution specific factor. In addition, self-help group specific factor was found positive and significantly ($\beta = 6.090$, t-value = 3.097) related to loan delinquency. Further external factor was found positive and significantly ($\beta = 2.549$, t-value = 2.069) related to loan delinquency performance in microfinance institutions in Kenya. The study concludes that microfinance institutions and self-help groups' specific factors and external factors significantly affect loan delinquency performance among microfinance institutions in Kenya. The study recommends that microfinance institutions portfolios management strategies focus more on the internal causes of delinquency which they have more control over and seek practical and achievable solutions to redress delinquency problems.

Sunil S. et al. (2021) in India carried out a study on factors influencing the borrower loan size in microfinance institutions group lending in India. The analysis is based on the primary data collected from a sample of 498 microfinance institutions linked group clients covering two microfinance leading states of India. Findings suggest that the cost of microfinance intermediation has an impact on borrowers' loan size. To reduce the cost, the microfinance lends big loans to clients having a high income, assets, land size, lower

informal borrowings and having longer experiences. In microfinance lending, the younger and less educated people are the ones who demand bigger loan amounts. The geographical distance of borrowers' location from microfinance group size and interest rate are the other factors that influence the loan size.

Literature on regulations of microfinance institutions

Many scholars have attempted answering the above mentioned questions in various ways in the literature.

Abdulai A. (2020) carried out a study in Sub-Saharan Africa on the impact on regulation on microfinance institutions sustainability and outreach. The investigation was done across ten countries for a period of 10 years using the dynamic generalized method of moment estimation technique. The study found empirical evidence that regulations have positive significant impacts on both the sustainability and depth of outreach performance of microfinance institutions.

In terms of magnitude, the impacts are greater on sustainability than on the depth of outreach. The study recommends that managers and board of directors of unregulated microfinance institutions should take steps to get them regulated through proper budgeting to meet regulatory costs, minimum capital requirements, and engage more with regulatory authorities. Also, regulatory authorities (Central Banks) should step up the monitoring and supervision and ensure full compliance with regulatory guidelines by microfinance institutions to help protect depositors and the financial system as a whole.

Furthermore, Pati A. (2015) carried out a study in India on the topic: are regulatory microfinance institutions in India better off than non-regulatory ones? This article, an empirical study has been made to compare the social (outreach related) and financial (cost, profit and sustainability related) performance of regulated microfinance institutions with non-regulated MFIs and to identify the causal variables of such performances. With the help of a panel data set of the last five years, that is, from 2008-2009 to 2012-2013 it is found that the preference of Indian MFIs for regulatory structure has culminated with better performance. Though the causal study, which is performed through the fixed-effect regression model, no impact of regulation is visible. Among the important explaining variables capital structure, the size of operating expenditure and quality of assets are found to be prominently responsible for outreach and sustainability of Indian microfinance institutions.

Mukiri S. (2013) in Kenya further carried out a research on the effect of government regulation on the financial sustainability of microfinance institutions. A sample of 30 retail microfinance institutions was drawn from a target population of 48 retail microfinance institutions in Kenya using disproportionate stratified random sampling for this study. Secondary data was collected from audited financial statements for each institution for 3 years and analysed using a multivariate regression model. The study found that capital adequacy and liquidity requirements had a positive effect on the financial sustainability of microfinance institutions with less than 50% positive correlation

on the financial sustainability and less than 50% negative correlation on the financial sustainability of microfinance institutions.

Nevertheless, Nyanzu et al. (2016) researched on Regulation, outreach and sustainability of microfinance institutions in Sub Saharan Africa: A multilevel analysis. This paper brings together issues lingering around regulations in microfinance institutions by examining an unbalanced panel data from 2002 to 2012 for 30 countries and employing multilevel estimation technique. The study reveals that regulation helps to improve the sustainability and breath of outreach but not depth of outreach. Also, country effect plays significant role in microfinance institutions activities. It is imperative for regulatory authorities to devise strategies to strengthen microfinance institutions financial position as well as ensuring enabling environment that will enhance the achievement of microfinance social objectives.

Nkendem F. et al. (2018) in Cameroon carried out a study on COBAC control measures on the performance of microfinance institutions. Data analysis for this study involved two major steps: the data reduction process and the structural relationship analysis. The data reduction process aimed to reduce the number of variables and parameters in the research model to a manageable number in terms of the ratio between sample size and parameters estimated in the structural equation modelling. The structural relationship analysis would be used to establish models for the Ordinal Regression analyses to examine the relationship between COBAC control measures and performance. The data reduction process was conducted in order to reduce the constructs employed in this study into composite variables. 10 constructs (solidarity funds as a percentage of Capital, Obligatory reserves control norms, Risk coverage control measures. Assets coverage control measures, Administrators, management and employees' engagement control norm, Credit resource ratio or transformation control measures. Ratio relative to line of financing received control measure, Liquidity control ratio, Ratio of highest debtor-highest debtor as a percentage of total debt control measure and Limit of other activities carried out control measures) constituted COBAC control measure latent variables, and 10 constructs of performance (profitability, customer satisfaction, bank liquidity, growth prospects, credit quality, distributable profits, risk exposure, credit strength, high amount of loans, distributable profit per share). These 10 constructs were subjected to validity and reliability test before a single score could be calculated to represent each construct. Confirmatory factor analysis using SPSS-20 (statistical package for social sciences) was employed for examining construct validity of each scale by assessing how well the individual item measured the scale. During this process, 5 items of COBAC control norms were retained and 4 items of performances were retained. The goodness of fit indices of the 5 constructs exceeded the 0.9 criterion that are required in establishing the construct validity. The reliability analysis was conducted by calculating the Cronbach's alpha for each scale. The result shows that the Cronbach's alpha measure for the constructs did not exceed the threshold point of 0.7 suggested by Nunnally (1967), but were at least 60% and this is encouraging given that the constructs are reported in the exploratory stage. The

final results of construct validity and reliability tests of the constructs are reported in his work. Having met the requirement of construct validity and reliability, the composite measure of each construct can be measured by calculating their mean values (Hair et al., 1998) and the models were given as shown below. The research findings revealed no significant relationship between source of information and the notion of microfinance institutions with reference to microfinance customers' perception. Again, there exist no significant relationship between various type of savings and voluntary savings following analysed information obtained from microfinance customers. Thus, voluntary savings was the main form of savings. Findings revealed that, customers often deposit cash mostly during months' end and was the popular form of transaction and, most customers had access to credit facilities following loan application. Majority of applied loan often last from one month to three months mostly for home keeping activities, business activities and payment of children school requirements. However, proof of physical collateral was the popular form collateral presented to authorities before loan approval. A good number of respondents affirmed in prompt payment of loan most having obtained loan less than one hundred thousand FCFA. It was envisaged that majority of respondents strongly agreed that microfinances are essential for socio-economic development. COBAC control mechanism in terms of prudential and non-prudential norms revealed that majority customers of microfinance within study area often encountered problems of high interest rate on loan, communication gaps and inadequate awareness, limited management and slow action to services.

At a 5% significant level, a significant strong relationship existed between location and impact of COBAC regulations on microfinance according to authorities. Thus, supervisory authorities and institutions to certify microfinance institutions in Cameroon makes the sector to remain fragile and suffers from disorder that makes it difficult to control, challenges in realizing collateral from customers among others.

Fotabong L. et al. (2016) researched on analysing the causes and evolution of loan delinquency/arrears within microfinance institutions in Cameroon. Multiple regression analysis was used to establish relationship between loan delinquency and the identified external factors. The regression results obtained indicates Legislative issue is the core external cause of microfinance institutions loan delinquency. Contagion effect and economic downturn were identified to be statistically insignificant. They concluded that in addition to profit motive (internal cause), Legislative issue as an external factor contribute significantly to the alarming rate of Loan Delinquency in microfinance institutions. To overcome this challenge requires a collective effort both from the regulatory authorities, the government, the banking commission and above all the general assembly of these institutions. The paper finally contends that major stakeholders in our sampled institutions have failed in their roles to strengthened microfinance institutions sufficiently to cope with rising challenges in the market. The paper considers delinquency management as a gauge not only for microfinance institutions sustainability but as a

means to boost deteriorating customers' confidence. We shall now move to chapter three which is research methodology.

3. Methodology Research Design

Survey research design are procedures in quantitative research in which investigators administer a survey to a sample or entire population of people to describe the attitudes, opinion, behaviours, or characteristics of the population. This design has the advantage of measuring current attitudes of practices. A survey research design has been used to administer questionnaires to 22 microfinance institutions in Ndian and Meme divisions.

Area of the Study

The study area covers both Ndian and Meme divisions of the South West Region of Cameroon.

Ndian division was formed in 1975 from part of Kumba and Victoria divisions and is one of six administrative units that constitute the South West Region. Its headquarters is in Mundemba and other major towns include Ekondo titi, Bamusso, Isangele, Toko, Bekora and Dikome Balue. A total of nine municipalities (Bamusso, Dikome Balue, Ekondo Titi, Idabator, Isangele, Kumbo Abedimo, Kumbo Itindi, Mundemba and Toko) make up the division and spread across an estimated surface area of about 6,626 km² (2,558 sq mi) 25% of the region). The division is linked to other major towns of Cameroon such as Kumba in the Meme Division by the national road N16 and which passes through Ekondo Titi onwards to Mundemba and Isangele. The division borders the Federal Republic of Nigeria to the west, Fako division to the south, Manyu division to the north and Meme and Kupe Muanenguba divisions to the east. A mangroves and creeks dominated estuary forms a very low and indented point of contact with the sea in the Rio del Rey estuary. This is in the eastern most part of the Gulf of Guinea known as the Bight of Biafra and which makes up over 35% of Ndian division. This estuary also forms the delta zone of the Ndian River with enormous ongoing marine erosion due to offshore oil drilling. Apart from this amphibious area which is dominated by mangroves and creeks, over 25% of the land surface is flat while about 40%, rests on the Rumpi Highlands. From a 2005 population survey and future projections, the population of Ndian division is estimated at 362,201, of which 17% are semi-urban and 83% rural.

Population of the Study and Sampling Procedure

The study focuses on category one and two microfinance institutions, that is, those operating within a network. Twenty-two microfinance institutions were selected and a panel data that captured information for six years period was used.

Those targeted as respondents to the questionnaires were the managers and loan officers of the various microfinance institutions.

Types of Data Collection

The data collecting instrument that was employed in the study was questionnaires. The researcher distributed 22 questionnaires to 22 microfinance institutions but initiated a panel data that captures information from 2015- 2020 giving a total sample of 22 microfinance institutions all together. A panel data is a multi-dimensional data that generally involve measurements of some periods of time.

Method of Data Collection

In this study data was collected through the use of questionnaires. These questionnaires were prepared and issued to category one Microfinance institutions in Ndian and Meme divisions who are carrying out lending activities as their major sources of income in a 2 times period from 2015 - 2020. In Ndian Division 5 microfinance institutions were issued questionnaires. While 17 microfinance institutions were selected in Kumba given a total of 22 microfinance institutions.

Table 1: Names and location of selected microfinance in Ndian and Meme Divisions.

Credit Union Code	Name of Credit Union	Location
1	Ndian Estate Cooperative Credit Union Ltd MFI	Mundemba
2	Lobe Cooperative Credit Union Ltd MFI	Ekondo Titi
3	Bambili Cooperative Credit Union Ltd MFI	Ekondo Titi
4	MC ² Ekondo Titi	Ekondo Titi
5	Bai Estate Cooperative Credit Union	Bai Estate
6	Mbonge CDC Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
7	Mbonge community Cooperative Credit Union	Kumba
8	Kumba town Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
9	Kumba Central Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
10	Agri-Workers Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
11	Self-Reliance Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
12	Mokunje Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
13	AZIRE Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
14	BAMENDA POLICE Cooperative Credit union,	Kumba
15	NTARIKON Cooperative Credit union,	Kumba
16	BAFUT Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
17	MMEN Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
18	NFONDONG Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
19	MBENGWI CENTRAL Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
20	COMMUNITY CREDIT COMPANY	Kumba

21	GUZANG Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
22	MUTUEL CREDIT COMPANY	Kumba

Equal distribution of the questionnaire was done.

Techniques of Analysis

a) Fixed Effects Model

The role states that we should use fixed-effects (FE) whenever you are only interested in analysing the impact of variables that vary over time. Fixed-effect explore the relationship between predictor and outcome variables within an entity (country, person, company, etc.). Each entity has its own individual characteristics that may or may not influence the predictor variables

When using fixed-effect we assume that something within the individual may impact or bias the predictor or outcome variables and we need to control for this. This is the rationale behind the assumption of the correlation between entity's error term and predictor variables. Fixed-effect remove the effect of those time-invariant characteristics so we can assess the net effect of the predictors on the outcome variable.

Another important assumption of the Fixed-effect model is that those time-invariant characteristics are unique to the individual and should not be correlated with other individual characteristics.

The fixed-effect model controls for all time-invariant differences between the individuals, so the estimated coefficients of the fixed-effects models cannot be biased because of omitted time-invariant characteristics (like culture, religion, gender, race, etc.).

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1,it} + \dots + \beta_k X_{k,it} + \gamma_2 E_2 + \dots + \gamma_n E_n + u_{it}$$

Where:

Y_{it} = Loan Delinquency as a measure of sustainability (dependent variable) where i = entity and t = time.

X_{1it} = Amount of unpaid loans in FCFA of the i^{th} Microfinance at the t^{th} time.

X_{2it} = Expenses of loans recovered in FCFA of the i^{th} Microfinance at the t^{th} time

X_{3it} = Regulations measured as COBAC prudential norms on a scale of 14, of the i^{th} Microfinance institution at the t^{th} time

β_k = coefficients for the Independent variables.

u_{it} = error term

E_n = entity n .

γ_2 = coefficient for the binary repressors (entities)

b) Random-Effects Model

Random-effect models are statistical models in which some of the parameters that define systematic components of the model exhibit some form of random variation. In random-effect models, some of these systematic effects are considered random. Randomness in

statistical models usually arises as a result of random sampling of units in data collection. When effects can have different values for each unit that is sampled, it is natural to think of them as random effects.

The rationale behind random effects model is that, unlike the fixed effects model, the variation across entities is assumed to be random and uncorrelated with the predictor or independent variables included in the model.

The crucial distinction between fixed and random effects is whether the unobserved individual effect embodies elements that are correlated with the regressors in the model, not whether these effects are stochastic or not (Green, 2008, p.183).

$$Y_{it} = \beta X_{it} + \alpha + u_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where:

μ_{it} = Between Micro Finance error

ε_{it} = Within Micro Finance error

β_k = Coefficients for the Independent variables (Unpaid Loans, Expenses Recovered and Regulations)

a = Intercept

The Model of the Study

This study made use of a multiple linear regression model in the analysis of the objectives. The multiple linear regressions is chosen because it helps to determine the relationship between a dependent variable and two or more predictor variables (Hair et al., 2010). In this study, the dependent variable is loan delinquency as a measure of sustainability. The main independent variables include: delayed payments, recovery cost and regulations. The study will be guided by the following regression model to establish the relationship

between the study variables. $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \varepsilon$

Where

Y = Loan delinquency as a measure of sustainability.

β_0 is the constant (The intercept of the model)

$\beta_1, \beta_2,$ and β_3 are parameter estimates

Independent variables of interest

X_1 = Amount of unpaid loans in FCFA

X_2 = Expenses of loans recovered in FCFA

X_3 = Regulations measured as COBAC prudential norms on a scale of 14.

ε = error term.

The model can be expressed mathematically as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Amount of unpaid loans} + \beta_2 \text{Expenses Amount of loans recovered} + \beta_3 \text{Regulations} + \varepsilon$$

4. Presentation of Findings

Descriptive statistics

Trend of Loan Delinquency (LD) of various panels

The chart below shows a brief summary of the trend of Loan Delinquency (LD) of the various Microfinances used in this study.

Figure 4. 1: Trend of Loan Delinquency in the various Micro finance institutions

Source: Field survey (2022)

Table 2: Name of microfinance Institutions and their Codes as used in this study.

Code	Name of MFI	Location
A	Ndian Estate Cooperative Credit Union Ltd MFI	Mundemba
B	Lobe Cooperative Credit Union Ltd MFI	Ekondo Titi
C	Bambili Cooperative Credit Union Ltd MFI	Ekondo Titi
D	MC ² Ekondo Titi	Ekondo Titi
E	Bai Estate Cooperative Credit Union	Bai Estate
F	Mbonge CDC Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
G	Mbonge community Cooperative Credit Union	Kumba
H	Kumba town Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
I	Kumba Central Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
J	Agri-Workers Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
K	Self-Reliance Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
L	Mokunje Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
M	AZIRE Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
N	BAMENDA POLICE Cooperative Credit union,	Kumba

O	NTARIKON Cooperative Credit union,	Kumba
P	BAFUT Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
Q	MMEN Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
R	NFONDONG Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
S	MBENGWI CENTRAL Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
T	COMMUNITY CREDIT COMPANY	Kumba
U	GUZANG Cooperative Credit union	Kumba
V	MUTUEL CREDIT COMPANY	Kumba

Source: Field survey (2022)

Regression results

The effect on loan delinquency can be explained using two possible models. A fixed effect model and a random effect model. The Random effect model believes that the determinants for Loan delinquency are more related to the policies of CAMCUL towards her Micro financial institutions while the random effect model believes that, the determinants of loan delinquency is as results of a fixed attribute associated by each micro finance institution.

Fixed Effect Model

The fixed-effects model controls for all time-invariant differences between the individuals, so the estimated coefficients of the fixed-effects models cannot be biased because of omitted time-invariant characteristics like culture, religion, gender, race, etc. in the individual Microfinance.

One side effect of the features of fixed-effects models is that they cannot be used to investigate time-invariant causes of the dependent variables (Loan Delinquency). Technically, time-invariant characteristics of the individuals are perfectly collinear with the microfinance dummies.

Substantively, fixed-effects models are designed to study the causes of changes within a microfinance institution. A time-invariant characteristic cannot cause such a change, because it is constant for each person.

Random Effect model

The rationale behind random effects model is that, unlike the fixed effects model, the variation across is assumed to be random and uncorrelated with the predictor or independent variables included in the model:

The crucial distinction between fixed and random effects is whether the unobserved individual effect embodies elements that are correlated with the regressors in the model, not whether these effects are stochastic or not.

If there are reason to believe that differences across Microfinance have some influence on our Loan Delinquency then the research will use random effects.

An advantage of random effects is that you can include time invariant variables (i.e. gender). In the fixed effects model these variables are absorbed by the intercept.

Table 3: Random effect model

Loan Delinquency	Coefficient	Standard error	Z-score	P> z	95% Conf. Interval	
Unpaid Loans	0.0261709	0.0077919	3.36	0.001	0.0108991	.0414427
Regulations	-2106508	713430.5	-2.95	0.003	-3504806	-708210
Expenses of loans recovered	0.0030727	0.065297	0.05	0.962	-0.124907	0.1310525
Constant term	3.67e+07	9272942	3.96	0.000	1.85e+07	5.49e+07

Source: Computed using STATA 14 on CAMCUL Survey data (2022)

The results shows that Unpaid Loans and COBAC Regulations are significant. The result shows that the coefficient of Unpaid Loans is 0.0261709 and the p-value is 0.001 which is positive and has a significant influence on the dependent variable loan delinquency.

The coefficient of COBAC Regulations is -2106508 and the p-value is 0.003 which is significant. It shows that COBAC Regulations has a significant influence on the dependent variable loan delinquency.

The coefficient of Expenses of loans recovered is 0.0030727 and the p-value is 0.962 which is higher than 0.05. This means that the result of ELR is not significant. ULR does not have a significant influence on the dependent variable loan delinquency.

Hausman Test

To decide between fixed or random effects we run a Hausman test where the null hypothesis is that the preferred model is random effects versus the alternative that the fixed effects is preferred. It basically tests whether the unique errors (*ui*) are correlated with the regressors, the null hypothesis is that, they are not correlated.

Table 4: Hausman Test

	Coefficients			
	(b) fixed	(B) random	(b-B) Difference	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B)) S.E.
ul	.0280526	.0261709	.0018817	.0038059
r	-2209169	-2106508	-102661.2	219445.7
elr	-.0070427	.0030727	-.0101154	.0128461

b = consistent under Ho and Ha; obtained from xtreg

B = inconsistent under Ha, efficient under Ho; obtained from xtreg

Test: Ho: difference in coefficients not systematic

$$\begin{aligned} \chi^2(1) &= (b-B)'[(V_b-V_B)^{-1}](b-B) \\ &= 0.22 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Prob}>\chi^2 = 0.6399$$

Source: Computed using STATA 14 on CAMCUL Survey data (2022)

The hypothesis for the model selection can be re stated as:

H₀: Radom effect is preferred

H₁: Fixed effect is preferred

The P value is 0.6399 which is not less than 0.01 (1% level of significance). Hence the random effect model is appropriate for this study. This means that the main effect on Loan Delinquency is best explained from the actions of CAMCUL rather than the individual activities of the various Microfinance.

Discussion of Result

The result indicate that the coefficient of unpaid loans is very significant in affecting loan delinquency of microfinance institutions and has a positive relationship. A unit increase in unpaid loans will lead to an increase in loan delinquency of individual microfinance institution. When this occurs the microfinance becomes more vulnerable towards sustainability. This finding is in line with the work of Theodosios A. (2020) who revealed that sustainability risk management indeed exist but it has yet to penetrate core processes. Managers at all level of the organizational hierarchy acknowledges the importance of sustainability oriented lending. Ruth E. et al. (2019) in Cameroon found out that there were a good number of lapses like high provision, poor recovery procedure, credit officers without an educational background in the field, manual execution of some loans, slow credit management processes, bad faith of customers and poor follow up of loans given out. It is true that when loans are unpaid, it brings about high consequences. This is in line with Paul H (2016) who found that late payment has wide range of consequences. Late payment of loans increases loan delinquency which will require follow up of these loans hence operational cost is as well increased. When this occurs, the sustainability of the microfinance institution is impacted negatively. This is in accordance with the work of Gideon A. (2018) who found out that several microfinance institutions struggle with high default rates and also charged high interest rate which has a negative influence on sustainability.

The result in this study further revealed that the variable 'expenses on loan recovered' has no significant impact on loan delinquency. The coefficient is not significant in affecting the relationship between expenses on loan recovered and loan delinquency. Though this study is showing no significance impact on loan delinquency, Zahid, et al. (2014) result of their study suggest that there are two key factors that are significantly related to microfinance institutions sustainability. Interest rate spread and general administrative costs. However, the study of Zahid et al. (2014) is different from this study the effect of loan delinquency on sustainability of microfinance institutions in Ndiain and Meme divisions of the South West Region of Cameroon.

Furthermore, Sunil S. et al. (2021) findings carried out in India, suggest that cost of microfinance intermediation has an impact on borrowers' loan size while in this study

expenses on loan recovered does not have any impact on loan delinquency hence sustainability of microfinance institutions is not affected.

This study also revealed that the variable 'role of regulations' has a significant effect on loan delinquency which leads to impacting the sustainability of microfinance institutions. This finding is in line with the work of Abdulai A. who found empirical evidence that regulations have positive significant impacts on both the sustainability and depth of outreach performance of microfinance institutions. Arguably, Pati A. (2015) in India with the help of panel data set found that regulatory microfinance performed better than non-regulatory microfinance institutions. More so, the work of Mukiri S. (2013) found that capital adequacy and liquidity requirements had a positive effect on the financial sustainability of microfinance institutions. Apart from that, the study of Nyanzu et al. (2016) revealed that regulation helps to improve the sustainability and breath of outreach of microfinance institutions in Sub Saharan Africa. This is in agreement with the result of this research work. Going further, the study of Nkendem F. et al. (2018) revealed that at 5% significant level, a significant strong relationship existed between location and impact of COBAC regulations on microfinance according to authorities. Fotabong L. et al. (2016) found that legislative issue is the core external cause of microfinance institutions loan delinquency.

This research work focused on, 'the effect of loan delinquency on the sustainability of microfinance institution in Ndian and Meme divisions of the South West Region of Cameroon. There are other variables that have affected the sustainability of microfinance institutions in Ndian and Meme division that were not taken into consideration. But it is necessary to discuss them at this level. The qualification of managers. More qualified managers will produce better result than less qualified ones. The crisis in the North West and South West Regions of Cameroon. Many microfinance institutions shut down their doors especially in Ndian division due to the crisis. Notably, Express Union in Ekondo Titi and Mundemba, EMI Money in Ekondo Titi and Express Exchange in Ekondo Titi and Mundemba. This demonstrate that three microfinance institutions operating in Ndian division could no longer operate due to political instability in the region. This therefore means that it is not only effect of loan delinquency that can impact sustainability of microfinance institutions. Economic down turn caused by instability in the economic environment can caused many microfinance institutions not to be stable. The main economic operator in Ndian division shut down. The workers of this Agro-industrial complex have huge loans portfolio which they had contracted in these microfinance institutions before the crisis which remains unpaid. Their salaries which could no longer be paid were the only means of payment. These unpaid loans have contributed negatively to increase the loan delinquency of these microfinance institutions affecting them negatively. The sustainability of these institutions is put in jeopardy. Many borrowers of these microfinance institutions have relocated and change their telephone contacts, some are death and loans abandoned. Some collaterals have been burnt and the microfinance will not be able to recover their loans. There is no doubt that most of these institutions are

faced with liquidity problems. The cash flow has drastically reduced to grant further loans to their customers. Their equity is gradually becoming negative due to consistent losses over the years.

Compliance of COBAC prudential norms are not met. This attract sanctions which may lead to shut down if losses persist.

This study was conducted with the main aim to examine the effect of loan policies on the sustainability of microfinance institutions in Ndian and Meme divisions of the South West Region in Cameroon. Many see microfinance institutions as an answer to low income earners, a means to promote economic development, employment and growth as these institutions help support small businesses through microcredit. Microcredit deals with the provision of loan facilities to the low income earners. Providing financial services to 2.5 billion people who are “unbanked” could boost economic growth and opportunity for the world’s poor. (World Bank Group, 2012). The problem statement, that microfinance dominate the financial sector in Cameroon and news of their closure or having liquidity problems make prominent headlines in most newspaper and television channels. Sustainability comes from a Latin verb *sustinere*, to maintain, sustain, support, and endure. A loan is delinquent when it is past due. When a payment is late CGAP, 1999). There are three broad types of delinquency indicators: collection rate which measures amount actually paid against amount that have fallen due. Arrears rates which measures overdue amount against total loan amounts, and portfolio at risk rates which measure the outstanding balance of loans that are not being paid on time over the outstanding balance of total loan. (CGAP, 1999). Theories adopted in this study were related to lending and performance of loans in microfinance institutions which includes, modern portfolio theory, liquidity theory of credit, credit risk theory, tax theory of credit and credit default theory. COBAC regulations on a scale of 14 prudential norms was clearly spelt out. Empirical review was carried out on delay payment of loans, expenses on loans recovered and regulations of microfinance institutions. Technique of analysis is panel data fixed effect and random effects. The nature of the data in the study was primary data. Primary data was collected through the use of questionnaires. The targeted population of the study was category one and two microfinance institutions in Ndian and Meme division. Multiple linear regression model was used. The sample size was 22 and the targeted respondents were managers, loan officers, and branch managers of each financial institution. The result of the study revealed that loan delinquency has significant impact on sustainability of microfinance institutions.

5. Conclusion

This research is on the effect of loan policies on sustainability of microfinance institutions in Ndian and Meme Divisions of the South West Region in Cameroon. It has demonstrated that loan delinquency has significant correlation with sustainability of MFIs. When there is high loan delinquency in a microfinance institution, the sustainability of the institutions staggers and when loan delinquency reduces the microfinance becomes more sustainable. On status of loans on sustainability of

microfinance institutions, this study concluded that unpaid loans have significant effect on loan delinquency as a measure of sustainability of microfinance institutions. The study equally noted that expenses on loans recovered have no correlation with loan delinquency as a measure of sustainability and finally the role of regulation have significant effect on loan delinquency as a measure of sustainability of microfinance institutions.

The researcher concluded that the external environment contributes significantly to the alarming rate of Loan Delinquency in microfinance institutions in Ndiain and Meme Divisions.

Recommendations

The study recommends that microfinance institutions portfolios management strategies should focus more on the internal causes of delinquency which they have more control over and seek practical and achievable solutions to redress delinquency problems.

Loan is the largest assets in microfinance institutions. Therefore, more attention should be geared towards ensuring efficient and effective management of loan portfolio to avoid delay payments of loans and unpaid loans becoming doubtful loans.

Loan officers should ensure that reminder letters are issued to borrowers regularly including text messages. The board of directors should create an environment where borrowers are rewarded for prompt payments and discourage unscrupulous debtors.

Management and board of directors of microfinance institutions should adhere to the lending policies put in place. Managers and board of directors of microfinance institutions should take steps to get them regulated through proper budgeting to meet regulatory costs, minimum capital requirements, and engage more with regulatory authorities.

Borrowers should be honest when contracting loans from microfinance institutions knowing that money they are borrowing belongs to people.

The role played by microfinance institutions in economic development cannot be over emphasized. The state should develop schemes to support these institutions and grant them subventions. Also, regulatory authorities (Central Banks) should step up the monitoring and supervision and ensure full compliance with regulatory guidelines by microfinance institutions to help protect depositors and the financial system as a whole.

It is imperative for regulatory authorities to devise strategies to strengthen microfinance institutions financial position as well as ensuring enabling environment that will enhance the achievement of microfinance social objectives.

Further research can be carried out on the effect of loan policies on sustainability of microfinance institutions in Cameroon.

Appendix I: Survey Data

Credit union		Loan delinquency	Amount of unpaid loans in FCFA	Regulations measured as COBAC prudential norms on a scale of 14	Expenses of loans recovered in FCFA
CU	Year	LD	UL	R	ELR
1	2015	10,100,000	1,450,000	12	6,000,000
1	2016	12,000,000	1,420,000	12	7,000,000
1	2017	14,000,000	1,415,000	14	8,000,000
1	2018	19,000,000	600,000	14	14,000,000
1	2019	22,000,000	7,500,000	13	9,000,000
1	2020	20,000,000	18,000,000	13	15,000,000
2	2015	19,754,000	450,000,000	10	3,500,000
2	2016	14,304,000	350,000,000	12	4,000,000
2	2017	20,974,000	400,000,000	12	12,000,000
2	2018	6,008,000	900,000,000	12	18,000,000
2	2019	27,622,000	949,108,000	10	19,000,000
2	2020	24,700,000	950,000,000	11	209,000,000
3	2015	4,814,000	192,452,000	10	7,654,000
3	2016	89,887,000	314,557,000	5	5,835,000
3	2017	0	228,743,000	9	3,576,000
3	2018	17,932,000	274,658,000	10	3,566,000
3	2019	44,243,000	157,474,000	10	3,299,000
3	2020	103,947,000	253,582,000	7	4,317,000
4	2015	1,471,400	10,001,250	12	1,475,400
4	2016	900,374	11,000,400	12	1,916,400
4	2017	2,413,750	10,757,560	10	1,375,475
4	2018	5,741,350	9,467,975	9	1,445,750
4	2019	4,334,561	10,075,500	9	17,754,600
4	2020	4,436,710	9,747,540	12	14,346,000
5	2015	10,051,000	11,450,000	10	5,647,500
5	2016	9,043,500	19,751,000	13	4,751,200
5	2017	8,103,450	17,003,475	9	6,482,451
5	2018	9,151,200	18,450,700	9	5,467,112
5	2019	10,355,000	19,034,075	10	4,378,516
5	2020	10,257,550	17,171,700	7	5,734,716
6	2015	4,037,000	15,000,000	10	105,000
6	2016	1,924,000	17,400,000	9	230,000

6	2017	0	17,270,000	10	0
6	2018	9,846,000	67,000,000	9	0
6	2019	14,078,000	91,800,000	9	0
6	2020	2,861,000	0	10	0
7	2015	2,100,000	30,000,000	11	11,000,000
7	2016	4,000,000	44,000,000	8	10,900,000
7	2017	4,000,000	52,000,000	9	12,500,000
7	2018	15,000,000	65,000,000	10	12,800,000
7	2019	18,000,000	60,000,000	11	13,500,000
7	2020	20,000,000	55,000,000	9	15,500,000
8	2015	2,587,000	30,395,000	12	1,387,000
8	2016	4,060,000	46,218,000	12	906,000
8	2017	4,058,000	54,792,000	11	2,844,000
8	2018	23,144,000	69,607,000	7	2,487,000
8	2019	23,141,000	55,098,000	11	2,431,000
8	2020	21,054,000	49,099,000	8	1,763,000
9	2015	6,000,000	15,000,000	12	290,000
9	2016	10,000,000	14,000,000	12	275,000
9	2017	11,000,000	17,000,000	10	280,000
9	2018	14,000,000	18,000,000	12	267,000
9	2019	16,000,000	19,000,000	12	342,000
9	2020	15,000,000	20,000,000	11	335,000
10	2015	12,000,000	404,000,000	13	12,000,000
10	2016	14,000,000	675,000,000	12	13,000,000
10	2017	16,000,000	680,000,000	13	15,000,000
10	2018	16,000,000	742,000,000	12	16,000,000
10	2019	17,000,000	768,000,000	12	15,000,000
10	2020	16,500,000	765,000,000	12	16,000,000
11	2015	19,000,000	450,000,000	7	2,000,000
11	2016	20,000,000	600,000,000	8	3,000,000
11	2017	25,000,000	750,000,000	8	3,500,000
11	2018	42,000,000	900,000,000	9	5,000,000
11	2019	30,000,000	1,000,000,000	9	2,100,000
11	2020	32,000,000	1,300,000,000	9	2,300,000
12	2015	6,000,000	6,400,000	14	904,000
12	2016	8,000,000	9,000,000	14	700,350
12	2017	9,000,000	9,700,000	14	805,000
12	2018	9,000,000	10,300,000	13	810,000
12	2019	8,000,000	11,000,000	13	826,000

12	2020	7,000,000	11,300,000	13	814,500
13	2015	18,000,000	202,000,000	7	1,500,000
13	2016	17,000,000	300,000,000	7	2,000,000
13	2017	20,000,000	400,000,000	7	3,000,000
13	2018	19,000,000	450,000,000	8	3,500,000
13	2019	10,000,000	406,000,000	8	2,000,000
13	2020	15,000,000	408,000,000	8	2,700,000
14	2015	1,300,000	14,000,000	12	340,000
14	2016	1,200,000	19,000,000	12	310,000
14	2017	1,100,000	19,500,000	11	332,000
14	2018	1,200,000	19,000,000	9	321,000
14	2019	1,300,000	14,000,000	11	294,000
14	2020	1,500,000	19,500,000	11	314,000
15	2015	17,000,000	21,000,000	13	16,000,000
15	2016	28,000,000	34,000,000	13	14,000,000
15	2017	30,000,000	44,000,000	12	21,000,000
15	2018	35,000,000	49,000,000	13	21,000,000
15	2019	38,000,000	48,000,000	13	18,000,000
15	2020	45,000,000	47,000,000	13	11,000,000
16	2015	19,000,000	500,000,000	9	7,000,000
16	2016	20,000,000	600,000,000	9	5,000,000
16	2017	25,000,000	700,000,000	9	2,000,000
16	2018	40,000,000	900,000,000	10	3,000,000
16	2019	33,000,000	950,000,000	10	1,000,000
16	2020	32,000,000	990,000,000	9	950,000
17	2015	13,000,000	240,816,149	6	1,094,300
17	2016	13,000,000	512,980,857	6	665,400
17	2017	18,000,000	339,608,049	6	818,100
17	2018	28,000,000	355,645,167	8	767,650
17	2019	32,000,000	334,123,842	6	473,500
17	2020	35,000,000	358,166,417	5	820,700
18	2015	12,500,000	180,000,000	12	6,000,000
18	2016	13,700,000	230,000,000	12	7,000,000
18	2017	20,000,000	312,000,000	13	6,500,000
18	2018	18,000,000	424,000,000	11	7,500,000
18	2019	15,000,000	402,000,000	12	8,000,000
18	2020	20,000,000	445,000,000	12	8,500,000
19	2015	97,000,000	200,000,000	13	11,000,000
19	2016	95,000,000	195,000,000	12	10,000,000

19	2017	95,000,000	180,000,000	12	12,000,000
19	2018	100,000,000	300,000,000	8	15,000,000
19	2019	103,000,000	495,000,000	7	13,000,000
19	2020	120,000,000	400,000,000	7	25,000,000
20	2015	36,000,000	302,000,000	12	3,000,000
20	2016	35,000,000	323,000,000	12	7,000,000
20	2017	36,000,000	310,000,000	11	8,000,000
20	2018	51,000,000	450,000,000	11	10,000,000
20	2019	62,000,000	555,000,000	10	11,000,000
20	2020	98,000,000	607,000,000	10	15,000,000
21	2015	5,800,000	300,000,000	12	4,000,000
21	2016	6,800,000	250,000,000	12	4,500,000
21	2017	6,000,000	150,000,000	13	4,300,000
21	2018	17,000,000	500,000,000	8	7,000,000
21	2019	28,000,000	850,000,000	10	10,000,000
21	2020	35,000,000	900,000,000	10	15,000,000
22	2015	1,459,615	105,850,100	9	4,000,000
22	2016	20,179,963	161,842,475	13	4,500,000
22	2017	17,608,134	168,209,235	9	6,000,000
22	2018	26,992,950	224,657,748	4	10,000,000
22	2019	4,863,601	241,374,200	11	8,000,000
22	2020	0	231,855,476	3	9,000,000

OTHER TESTS / DIAGNOSTICS

Testing for time-fixed effects

```
. xi: xtreg ld ul r elr i.year, fe
i.year      _Iyear_2015-2020 (naturally coded; _Iyear_2015 omitted)
```

```
Fixed-effects (within) regression      Number of obs   =   132
Group variable: id                    Number of groups =    22
```

```
R-sq:                                Obs per group:
  within = 0.2652                      min =      6
  between = 0.0628                     avg =     6.0
  overall = 0.1097                     max =      6
                                     F(8,102)      =    4.60
corr(u_i, Xb) = 0.0015                 Prob > F      =   0.0001
```

```
-----+-----
      ld |   Coef.   Std. Err.   t   P>|t|   [95% Conf. Interval]
-----+-----
      ul |   .0133972   .0098793    1.36  0.178   -0.0061984   .0329928
      r  |  -1684354   759557.2   -2.22  0.029   -3190932   -177775.4
      elr |  -.0266795   .0660155   -0.40  0.687   -1.1576209   .1042619
  _Iyear_2016 |  4698395   3468639    1.35  0.179   -2181635   1.16e+07
  _Iyear_2017 |  1773519   3480893    0.51  0.612   -5130816   8677854
  _Iyear_2018 |  5786537   3761041    1.54  0.127   -1673470   1.32e+07
  _Iyear_2019 |  7975697   3830587    2.08  0.040   377745.8   1.56e+07
  _Iyear_2020 |  1.20e+07   4018583    2.99  0.003   4044719   2.00e+07
  _cons |  3.06e+07   8766768    3.49  0.001   1.32e+07   4.80e+07
-----+-----
sigma_u |  21080382
sigma_e |  11398570
rho     |  .7737678 (fraction of variance due to u_i)
```

```
F test that all u_i=0: F(21, 102) = 20.17      Prob > F = 0.0000
```

```
. testparm _Iyear*
```

- (1) _Iyear_2016 = 0
- (2) _Iyear_2017 = 0
- (3) _Iyear_2018 = 0
- (4) _Iyear_2019 = 0
- (5) _Iyear_2020 = 0

```
F( 5, 102) = 2.18
Prob > F = 0.0621
```

Testing for random effects: Breusch-Pagan Lagrange multiplier (LM)

Here we failed to reject the null and conclude that random effects is not appropriate. This is, no evidence of significant differences across countries, therefore you can run a simple OLS regression.

chi2 (22) = 21639.55

Prob>chi2 = 0.0000 (Presence of heteroskedasticity)

Testing for serial correlation

. xtserial ld ul r elr

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data

H0: no first order autocorrelation

F(1, 21) = 8.540

Prob > F = 0.0081 (there is serial correlation)

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